

Self-supervised Precoding Policies for MIMO Rate Splitting Multiple Access

Dheeraj Raja Kumar, Carles Antón-Haro and Xavier Mestre
Centre Tecnologic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/iCERCA)
Castelldefels, Barcelona
{dheeraj.raja.kumar, carles.anton, xavier.mestre}@cttc.es

Abstract—In this paper, we investigate the use of self-supervised data-driven schemes for precoder optimization in the downlink of a Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) system. Specifically, we propose two architectures based on Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) respectively, and analyze their achievable sum-rate performance in the overloaded regime as the system scales up. To that aim, we use conventional schemes such as Zero Forcing (ZF) or Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (WMMSE) precoding as benchmarks. Complementarily, we compare their complexity in terms of the number of trainable parameters and computation time. GNN-based scheme is found to exhibit an interesting performance-complexity and scalability trade-off.

Index Terms—Graph Neural Network, Deep Learning, Precoding, RSMA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) has been pointed out as a unifying framework of existing MA schemes - Orthogonal Multiple Access (OMA), Space Division Multiple Access (SDMA) and Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) [1]. RSMA has been shown to outperform NOMA [1] [2] in multi-input multi-output (MIMO) settings, both in terms of sum multiplexing gain and efficient use of Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC). RSMA enhances the benefits of MU-MIMO by achieving higher data rates and spectral efficiency, especially when users are closer together and under imperfect Channel State Information at Transmitter (CSIT). All these observations have led to the recommendation of 3GPP RAN to consider a study item on RSMA in Rel-19 [3].

The simplest and most practical RSMA scheme is 1-layer Rate Splitting (RS), which is the basic building block of almost all existing RSMA schemes. It involves transmission of common message symbols (common to all the users) followed by SIC and decoding of individual private messages (see Section II). The precoder optimization plays a key role in interference management of the common and private streams in the system. The widely adopted Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (WMMSE) algorithm has been applied in [2] [4] to obtain the precoders in RSMA system. On the contrary, [5] introduces Sampled Average Approximation (SAA)-WMMSE

method under known CSIT and CSIT error distribution. The application of the above variations of WMMSE is computationally intensive as the number of transmit antennas and users in the system increases. Alternatively, sub-optimal schemes involve the use of zero-forcing (ZF) for obtaining the private precoders and singular value decomposition (SVD) for the common stream [6] [7]. However, the system capacity achieved is not satisfactory, especially in large RSMA settings.

As for the application of Deep Learning (DL) to enhance the WMMSE algorithm, a number of works can be found in the literature [8]–[10]. Specific to RSMA scenario, the authors in [10] overly fit a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) to learn the precoders of WMMSE algorithm for one channel realization and use it as a starting reference for subsequent ones, inspired by meta-learning based precoder design. In [11], deep convolutional neural networks (CNN) are used in a supervised manner to learn the linear precoders for rate splitting of aerial computing networks. The above methods require labeled datasets (i.e., precoders from WMMSE variants) to train the neural networks in a supervised manner. Obtaining such large datasets is time consuming and inefficient for large RSMA settings. This can be avoided by training the system in a self-supervised manner [8] [12], that is, by resorting to a customized loss function dependent on the *channel response* instead of using precoder instances. Among self-supervised approaches, [12] looks into the use of transformers to perform precoder optimization in an end-to-end RSMA setting with analog and digital beamforming networks.

This paper investigates the use of Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) for RSMA precoder optimization. Since precoders are permutation equivariant with the channel matrix, GNN architecture offers more scalable solutions (e.g., reduced number of trainable parameters) for the MIMO beamforming optimization task [8]. For this reason, here we extend the application of GNN for RSMA beamforming and compare its performance to MLPs and other existing benchmarks. Similar to [12], we train the neural networks in a self-supervised manner to output the precoders. We evaluate the performance-complexity trade-off involved in the usage of lighter models (shallow and deep architectures) which are not as computationally intensive as the transformers used in [11]. The computation time [10] of the proposed precoding schemes for large user settings is evaluated against WMMSE [2]. We also study the impact of CSIT error on the robustness of the

This work was supported by grants PID2021-128373OB-I00, PRE2019-089309 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of making Europe,” also by the Spanish ministry of economic affairs and digital transformation and of the European union – NextGenerationEU[UNICO-5G I+D/AROMA3D-Earth(TSI-063000- 2021-69).

Fig. 1. One-layer RS model with K users. The common stream s_c is intended for all users, whereas private streams s_k are individual to each user.

precoder optimization policies.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In downlink of a multi-user RSMA system, the Base Station (BS) is equipped with N_T transmit antennas that serves K single-antenna users. We consider 1-layer RS in this paper, where the message W_k intended for the k -th user is split at the transmitter into two sub-messages namely, sub-message $W_{c,k}$ and private sub-message $W_{p,k}$. The sub-messages $W_{c,1}, \dots, W_{c,K}$ of all the users are combined into one message W_c and encoded into a common stream s_c using a codebook shared by all users. Although the entire common message W_c has to be decoded by all users, only the corresponding sub-message $W_{c,k}$ is of interest to the k -th user. The private sub-messages of all users $W_{p,1}, \dots, W_{p,K}$ are independently encoded into private streams s_1, \dots, s_K , which are decoded by the respective users (illustrated in Figure 1). Therefore, $K + 1$ streams, i.e. $\mathbf{s} = [s_c, s_1, \dots, s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{(K+1) \times 1}$ are created from the K messages W_1, \dots, W_K .

The streams are then linearly transformed via multiplication with the precoding matrix $\mathbf{P} = [\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_K]$ where $\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times 1}$, $k = 1, \dots, K$ are the unit-norm beamforming vectors. The transmit signal thus reads

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} = \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a diagonal matrix containing the values $\alpha_c, \alpha_k \in [0, 1]$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$, which are the power allocation coefficients of common and private message streams. They are assumed to be normalized, such that $\alpha_c^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^2 = 1$. The received signal at k -th user is thus given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}_k \\ &= \mathbf{h}_k \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \mathbf{h}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k + \sum_{j \neq k} \mathbf{h}_k \alpha_j \mathbf{p}_j s_j + \mathbf{n}_k \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times N_T}$ is the channel vector of the k -th user modeled as Gaussian random variables with the entries being circularly symmetric and drawn independently for each

realization; \mathbf{n}_k denotes i.i.d. Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance $\sigma_{n,k}^2$.

At the receiver, each user first decodes the common stream s_c into W_c by treating the interference from all private streams as noise. Using Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC), W_c is then re-encoded, precoded, and subtracted from the received signal such that user- k decodes its private stream s_k into $W_{p,k}$ by treating the remaining interference from the other private streams as noise. Finally, the k -th user reconstructs the original message by extracting $W_{c,k}$ from W_c , and combining $W_{c,k}$ with $W_{p,k}$ into W_k . The signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) at k -th user for decoding the common and private streams are given by the respective equations below.

$$\gamma_{c,k} = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k^H \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c|^2}{\sum_{q=1}^K |\mathbf{h}_k^H \alpha_q \mathbf{p}_q|^2 + \sigma_{n,k}^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_{p,k} = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k^H \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k|^2}{\sum_{q=1, q \neq k}^K |\mathbf{h}_k^H \alpha_q \mathbf{p}_q|^2 + \sigma_{n,k}^2}. \quad (4)$$

The achievable rate of the common stream of k -th user is $R_{c,k} = \log_2(1 + \gamma_{c,k})$, while that of the private stream is $R_{p,k} = \log_2(1 + \gamma_{p,k})$. As the common stream must be decoded by all the users in the system, it must be transmitted at a rate not exceeding a global common minimum, namely, $R_c = \min\{R_{c,1}, \dots, R_{c,K}\}$. Thus, the achievable sum-rate R_{sum} for a precoding matrix \mathbf{P} reads

$$R_{\text{sum}}(\mathbf{P}) = R_c + \sum_{k=1}^K R_k \quad (5)$$

A. Optimum and Conventional Precoder Solutions

To compute the precoders of the RSMA system, [2] [5] adopt the classical Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (WMMSE) algorithm using Sampled Average Approximation (SAA) method. Being an iterative solution, the WMMSE benchmark serves as the upper-bound of the achievable sum rate (upon reaching convergence). However, SAA-WMMSE becomes computationally intensive and takes longer time to converge when the system setup scales up (higher number of transmit antennas or/and users). The algorithm [2], in particular, involves finding a closed-form solution for computing scalar equalizers \mathbf{G} and user weights \mathbf{U} for a given precoding matrix \mathbf{P} , which are optimized alternatively in each iteration. The problem is a convex Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Program (QCQP) which can be solved using interior-point methods [5]. The optimization of (5) requires the use of CVX toolbox which demands a very high number of operations as the system scales up [2] [12].

There exist sub-optimal solutions with lower complexity, as shown in [6] [7]. The common precoder \mathbf{p}_c is designed as the principal eigenvector (i.e., eigenvector associated to the largest eigenvalue) of the overall channel matrix. This guarantees that the transmitted power is maximized towards all the directions where users are present, without per-user priorities. The precoder vectors associated to the private streams are built such that they are completely orthogonal to one another using zero-forcing.

III. NEURAL NETWORKS FOR PRECODING

In this section, we formulate the problem of precoder optimization such that it can be solved using neural networks (NN). Specifically, we look into the use of Graph Neural Network (GNN), shallow (one layer) and deep architectures of Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) based solutions.

A. Problem Formulation

The precoders are optimized to maximize the sum-rate R_{sum} of the system as defined in (5) subject to a set of constraints:

$$\max_{\mathbf{P}} R_{\text{sum}}(\mathbf{P}) = R_c + \sum_{k=1}^K R_k \quad (6)$$

$$\text{s.t. } R_c \leq R_{c,k}, \forall k \in K \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{P}\mathbf{P}^H) \leq P_t \quad (8)$$

where (7) follows from the discussion in Section II; and (8) is the transmit power constraint, with P_t standing for the total transmit power.

The neural network-based precoders considered in this work take as input the overall channel matrix $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{h}_K^T]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times N_T}$ and outputs the precoding matrix $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$. Thus, we have

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}} = f(\mathbf{H}; \theta)$$

where θ denotes the trainable parameters of the NN. In other words, the training of the NN is performed in a self-supervised manner by minimizing the negative of the sum rate, that is

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} -R_{\text{sum}}(f(\mathbf{H}; \theta)). \quad (9)$$

As the SINR of the common and private streams depend on the precoders, the neural networks are trained to achieve precoder optimization using gradient descent and backpropagation.

B. Graph Neural Network

The RSMA precoding problem can be represented as a mapping to be learnt from $K \times N_T$ channel matrix to $K \times (K+1)$ precoding matrix. The N_T transmit antennas and K users can be viewed as nodes of a graph, while the edges of the graph represent the MIMO channel, with $N_E = K \cdot N_T$ being the total number of edges of the graph (see Fig. 2). The L -layer GNN consists of: (i) one input layer depicting the wireless network as a graph with each of the edges containing the real values of channel coefficient; (ii) one output layer with each of the edges holding the estimated precoder coefficients; and (iii) $L-2$ hidden layers that implement the Message Passing Algorithm (MPA) with $d_l (l = 2, \dots, L-2)$ edge features each.

Message Passing Algorithm (MPA) The embedding of each edge (t, r) in layer l is represented as $z_{(t,r)}^l$ which holds the real and imaginary coefficients of the channel along the particular edge i.e., $z_{(t,r)}^l = [\text{Re}(h_{t,r}), \text{Im}(h_{t,r})]^T$. In each of the hidden layers, the operations consist of message-passing iterations and an update step, which is expressed as below

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}$ and $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}$ are the messages aggregated from the neighboring nodes of edge (t, r) , which is defined as

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)} = \text{AGGREGATE}^{(l)} \left(\{ \mathbf{z}_{(t,x)}^{(l)}, \forall x \in \mathcal{N}(t) \} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)} = \text{AGGREGATE}^{(l)} \left(\{ \mathbf{z}_{(x,r)}^{(l)}, \forall x \in \mathcal{N}(r) \} \right) \quad (12)$$

The mechanism of the message passing algorithm (MPA)

Fig. 2. GNN for RSMA precoder computation, visualized for a single edge $(0,0)$ in the graph. The message passing operations are shown in (a) message aggregation at transmit nodes $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}$ and (b) message aggregation at receive nodes $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}$, while (c) shows the updated edge feature as per update rule (10).

in the l -th hidden layer is shown in Figure 2. It should be noted that the UPDATE and AGGREGATE are differentiable functions [13] that need to be defined.

The update rule in (10) can be expanded as below

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$= \sigma \left(\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)} \mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)} + \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} + \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)}$ denotes the hidden representation of the edge (t, r) at the $(l+1)$ layer of the GNN, $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a non-linear activation function and the matrices $\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{l+1} \times d_l}$ are the learnable weights of GNN to be optimized using stochastic gradient descent. In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers [14]. At the output layer, a linear activation function is used to compute the precoders.

Similar to [15] [16], we define the message aggregation (via the AGGREGATE function in (11) and (12)) passed between the nodes as follows

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(t)|} \sum_{r' \in \mathcal{N}(t)} \mathbf{z}_{(t,r')}^{(l)} \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(r)|} \sum_{t' \in \mathcal{N}(r)} \mathbf{z}_{(t',r)}^{(l)} \quad (16)$$

The dimensions d_{l+1} and d_l of the weight matrices $\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)}$ determine the number of features in layers $(l+1)$ and l , respectively. For the RSMA precoding problem, the input layer of GNN has $d_0 = 2$ features (real and imaginary parts of the channel coefficient). The optimum number of edge features d_l of the hidden layers is found via

hyperparameter tuning. At the output layer, the learnt edge features are viewed as the learnt precoder values (real and imaginary parts of the precoding matrix). To fulfill the power constraint, a power normalization layer is applied to the output, which consists of a scalar normalization given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{\text{norm}} = \alpha \hat{\mathbf{P}} \quad (17)$$

with $\alpha = \sqrt{P_T / \text{Tr}(\hat{\mathbf{P}}\hat{\mathbf{P}}^H)}$. In this work, we employ one hidden layer for the GNN because of the simple nature of the input graph where all the transmit and user antennas are connected via edges. The message aggregated over one-hop neighborhood is able to gather relevant statistics for computing the precoder matrix, thus not requiring multiple layers which would be needed to aggregate information of nodes/edges over multiple hops [13].

C. Multi-Layer Perceptron

The self-supervised precoder design problem can also be solved via feed-forward Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). Specifically, it can be cast into a regression task where:

- The input of the DNN is the overall channel matrix \mathbf{H} re-shaped into a row vector $\mathbf{t} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{H}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{H}) \otimes [0, 1]]$.
- The output is the computed precoders $\mathbf{p} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\hat{\mathbf{P}}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\hat{\mathbf{P}}) \otimes [0, 1]]$

Feed-forward Deep Neural Networks includes the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). The L -layer MLP consists of: (i) one input layer with $2KN_T$ elements (the real and imaginary parts of the channel matrix); (ii) one output layer with $2N_T(K+1)$ neurons; and (iii) $L-2$ hidden layers with $N_l; l = 2, \dots, L-1$ neurons each. This MLP defines a mapping $f(\mathbf{t}, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_T}$ of an input vector \mathbf{t} onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L iterative processing steps:

$$\mathbf{r}_l = f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l); \quad l = 1 \dots L \quad (18)$$

where $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. Such mapping depends on the output from the previous layer and also the parameter set of the concerned layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model.

Similar to the previous architecture, ReLU is used as activation functions in all hidden layers. We do not use normalization and dropout layers as this was found to be counterproductive in most regression problems [17].

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we first assess the performance of the proposed *GNN* and *MLP* schemes in terms of the Achievable Sum-Rate (ASR), alongside the impact of CSIT error, and followed by the computational complexity of the precoding schemes. The scenarios considered are: $K = \{2, 8, 64\}$ single-antenna users, and $N_T = \{3, 9, 64\}$ transmit antennas, respectively. For the first two cases, they are highly loaded systems, meaning there are as many streams ($K+1$) as transmit antennas (N_T), whereas the final case is an overloaded system

with $N_T < (K+1)$. We train the neural networks in the described *self-supervised* manner to compute the precoders at SNR of 20dB. We use this set of precoders to compute the sum rate across a SNR range of -10dB to 30dB. For the stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad), the learning rate is set to 0.01. All the neural networks are trained for 100 epochs, to ensure they reach convergence.

We performed grid-search hyperparameter optimization in order to determine the N_l neurons of the shallow MLPs in the search space of $\{64-1024\}$ neurons. The optimal neurons for $K = [2, 8, 32, 64]$ users is $N_l = [128, 256, 512, 1024]$ neurons, respectively. For deep MLPs, we simply added two more hidden layers in order to boost the learning capacity. With respect to GNNs, the optimum number of edge features d_l in the hidden layers is 4 features, after performing hyperparameter tuning in the range of $[2, 4, 8]$.

A. Achievable Sum-Rate

The neural networks take as input the overall channel matrix \mathbf{H} to compute the precoders. As benchmarks, we have followed the implementation of WMMSE for RSMA [2] which serves as the upper-bound, while the sub-optimal solution based on zero-forcing (ZF) acts as the lower-bound. Additionally, we compute the precoders based on Regularized Zero-forcer (RZF) which is a scaled version of ZF, namely $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{RZF}} = \mathbf{H}^H (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H + \delta \mathbf{I})^{-1}$ where $\delta = \frac{1}{\text{SNR}}$.

Figure 3 depicts the achievable sum-rate as a function of the SNR for all the scenarios considered averaged for 100 channel realizations. For the case of $K=2$ users, the gap between ZF and WMMSE performance is marginal, with the neural networks exhibiting similar performance to ZF. In the case of $K=8$ users, neural network based precoders offer substantial gain in the mid-SNR region, when compared to ZF. On the contrary, in the more realistic overloaded scenario of 64 users, ZF and RZF do not offer satisfactory performance, whereas the performance of neural network-based schemes is virtually identical to that of the WMMSE algorithm for all SNRs. This is achieved at a much reduced computational time as it will be discussed in Section IV-C2 ahead. When compared to ZF, the neural network based schemes offer almost four orders of improvement at 20dB.

B. Impact of Channel Estimation

The quality of the channel state information at the transmitter (CSIT) may have a substantial impact on the achievable sum rate of the precoding policies. The noisy channel estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ (instead of \mathbf{H}) is modelled as $\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{H} + \mathbf{N}$, where $\mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times N_T}$ represents zero-mean AWGN of variance β^2 . With imperfect precoders, the orthogonality of the private messages is not preserved, leading to poor ASR. In Figure 4 (x-axis in log scale), one observes that the ASR decreases as the noise variance increases. The degradation rate has been analyzed at different SNR, solid lines depict for 30dB, while the dashed are for 20dB. For the system with 8 users (highly loaded scenario, top), ZF benchmark degrades faster than MLP and GNN schemes for $\beta^2 > 10^{-2}$. For 64 users (overloaded

Fig. 3. Achievable Sum-Rate of the precoder optimization solutions.

scenario, bottom), the NN schemes follow the descending pattern exhibited by the WMMSE benchmark. Shallow MLP records slightly lower performance than deep MLP, whereas GNN offers similar performance to deep MLP using reduced number of trainable parameters (see next section).

C. Computational Complexity Analysis

1) *Number of trainable parameters:* The total number of trainable parameters depends on (i) the number of hidden layers in the DNN, which, in this work, equals 1 for shallow MLPs and 3 for deep MLPs; (ii) the number of hidden features (d_l) for GNNs (iii) the number of inputs $2KN_T$; (iv) the

Fig. 4. Achievable Sum Rate for various precoding policies vs. noise variance β^2 of CSIT, for scenario with 8 users (top) and 64 users (bottom). The solid lines correspond to SNR 30dB, while the dashed are for 20dB.

number of neurons at the output layer, which is the total number of real values to be estimated (real and imaginary precoder matrix coefficients) $N_L = 2N_T(K + 1)$; (v) the number of neurons at the hidden layers (N_l) for DNNs.

As depicted in Figure 5, GNNs record the least number of trainable parameters compared to shallow and deep MLPs for the whole range of number of transmit antennas and users. This stark difference (note y-axis is in log-scale) is because in GNNs, the same weights ($\mathbf{W}_{edge}, \mathbf{W}_t, \mathbf{W}_r$) are used for each edge to compute the precoder coefficients, unlike MLP which demands higher number of neurons as the system scales up, validating that GNNs are scalable architectures.

2) *Computation Time:* In order to compare the neural network schemes against the conventional iterative WMMSE algorithm, we analyze the computation time required by each of the schemes. The algorithms are implemented in Python. Figure 6 (x-axis in log scale) reveals that the neural network precoding schemes require less time in reaching convergence. As pointed out in [10], [18], WMMSE algorithm is not computationally-friendly as the number of transmit antennas and users scale up. For both scenarios shown in the figure, WMMSE is the most time consuming algorithm. The neural

Fig. 5. Number of trainable parameters for each of the precoder optimization solutions ($N_T = \{3, 9, 32, 64\}$; $K = \{2, 8, 32, 64\}$).

Fig. 6. Computation time of the precoder optimization solutions.

networks are reaching convergence while WMMSE still completes the first iteration. We do not make a comparison of the MLP versus GNN schemes as different Python libraries are used for their respective implementation. GNN has been implemented using the PyTorch Geometric library [19], which is specifically built to easily code and train GNNs, while the MLPs are coded using PyTorch.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The use of machine learning based precoder policies has a clear advantage in terms of computation time when compared with traditional iterative based benchmarks. For MIMO-

RSMA setting, MLPs and GNNs trained in a self-supervised manner achieve similar performance to that of WMMSE solution and outperform sub-optimal ZF by several orders of magnitude in selected scenarios. GNNs prove to be a scalable solution requiring lesser trainable parameters, and without requiring much hyperparameter optimization/tuning like the MLPs. The study will be extended to cover the computational complexity in terms of number of operations and evaluating the NN based precoders in the presence of non-linear channels.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Clerckx, Y. Mao, R. Schober, and H. V. Poor, "Rate-splitting unifying SDMA, OMA, NOMA, and multicasting in MISO broadcast channel: A simple two-user rate analysis," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 9, pp. 349–353, 2020.
- [2] Y. Mao, B. Clerckx, and V. O. K. Li, "Rate-splitting multiple access for downlink communication systems: bridging, generalizing, and outperforming SDMA and NOMA," *Eurasip Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, 2018.
- [3] BBC, "Rate splitting multiple access (RSMA) for multi-user MIMO - enhancement of unicast and joint unicast/multicast delivery," *3GPP TSG RAN Rel-19 Workshop, RWS-230044*, June 2023.
- [4] H. Joudeh and B. Clerckx, "Rate-splitting for max-min fair multigroup multicast beamforming in overloaded systems," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 16, pp. 7276–7289, 2017.
- [5] H. Joudeh and B. Clerckx, "Robust transmission in downlink multiuser MISO systems: A rate-splitting approach," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 64, pp. 6227–6242, 2016.
- [6] A. Krishnamoorthy and R. Schober, "Downlink MIMO-RSMA with successive null-space precoding," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. PP, pp. 1–1, 2021.
- [7] D. Raja-Kumar, C. Antón-Haro, and X. Mestre, "RS-Net: Neural network-enhanced receivers for MIMO rate splitting multiple access," *Next Generation Multiple Access (NGMA) for Future Wireless Communications at IEEE GLOBECOM*, 2023.
- [8] B. Zhao, J. Guo, and C. Yang, "Learning precoding policy: CNN or GNN?," *2022 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, pp. 1027–1032, 2022.
- [9] L. Pellaco and J. Jald'en, "A matrix-inverse-free implementation of the MU-MIMO WMMSE beamforming algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 70, pp. 6360–6375, 2022.
- [10] R. C. Loli and B. Clerckx, "A meta-learning-based precoder optimization framework for rate-splitting multiple access," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 13, pp. 347–351, 2023.
- [11] Z. Wang, R. Ma, H. Shi, Z. Cai, L. Lin, and H. Guan, "Deep convolutional linear precoder neural network for rate splitting strategy of aerial computing networks," *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering*, 2024.
- [12] M. Wu, Z. Gao, C. Hu, and Z. Li, "Data-driven deep learning-based rate-splitting multiple access for FDD massive MIMO-OFDM systems with implicit CSI," *2023 IEEE 24th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, pp. 156–160, 2023.
- [13] W. L. Hamilton, "Graph representation learning," *Synthesis Lectures on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning*, 2020.
- [14] A. Géron, "Hands-on machine learning with scikit-learn and tensorflow: Concepts, tools, and techniques to build intelligent systems," 2017.
- [15] F. R. Thomas Feys, Liesbet Van der Perre, "Toward energy-efficient massive MIMO: Graph neural network precoding for mitigating non-linear PA distortion," *Arxiv*, 2023.
- [16] S. Cammerer, J. Hoydis, F. A. Aoudia, and A. Keller, "Graph neural networks for channel decoding," *2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, pp. 486–491, 2022.
- [17] S. Rasmussen, "Pitfalls with dropout and batchnorm in regression problems." Accessed: 2022-03-26.
- [18] L. van der Maaten and G. E. Hinton, "Visualizing data using t-sne," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 9, pp. 2579–2605, 2008.
- [19] P. Team, "Pytorch geometric library," Last Accessed April 2024.